

Supplementary Material - Appendix A: Annotation Policy, Dataset & Training Details

For “Real-time Shoplifting Detection with YOLOv10n
and Behavioural Thresholding”

Ali Nabhan Aboobakuru · Mohamed Shaus Saman ·
Aminath Reema

Villa College (QI Campus), Malé, Maldives

Metadata

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Contact: s2300612@students.villacollege.edu.mv

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Related resources:

• GitLab repository: <https://gitlab.uwe.ac.uk/an3-aboobakuru/shoplifting-detection-in-retail-environment>

• Colab (MLP):
<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1uiuwHEQRsVQQnUVay75CIjCjB7cfuJVt?usp=sharing>

• Colab (YOLO):
https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1rSue_nWjrI7_FpDiHp79-I7uW6tQN2Zk?usp=sharing

• Demo video:
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1epNjCsFXRnTIK3wxLe2_HHJ99AC4EuMh/view?usp=sharing

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Appendix A:

Appendix A.1 Annotation Policy: Occlusion & Attributes

A.1.1 General boxing & identity rules

- Axis-aligned boxes only. Do not rotate boxes; always use upright, tight boxes around the visible extent.
- Same identity across the clip. If a person or item leaves the frame and later re-enters, continue the same track (do not create a new one).
- Annotate every frame the instance is visible. Use CVAT interpolation to keep boxes tight as size/position change.

A.1.2 Visibility / occlusion definitions

We use three states: visible, occluded, out-of-view (no box).

Person

- Visible: more than half of the person’s body is visible. Keep the track active.
- Occluded: annotate as present (box kept) when either (i) ≥ 2 limbs are mostly hidden or (ii) head + upper torso is hidden by objects/people or by the camera crop. The box should still cover the visible remainder.
- Out-of-view: if the person is fully outside the frame, keep the track but with no box until they re-appear (resume with the same ID).

Item

- Visible: draw a box from the first moment the shoplifter interacts with it.
- Occluded: keep the box while $< \sim 75\%$ of the item remains visible (approximate judgement).
- Out-of-view / fully hidden: no box (the track remains for attribute state, see below).

Table A.1.1: Attribute state rules (when to switch ON/OFF)

Entity	Attribute	Turn ON when...	Turn OFF when...
Person	suspicious_behavior	The person looks around for	Keep ON for the remainder of the clip once

		people/cameras or repeatedly inspects the same item/area.	concealment begins (for continuity).	video sources, then manually annotated frames in CVAT for the classes person (0) and item (1). Splits were made by video ID to avoid leakage.			
Person	concealing_item	The action of concealing begins (e.g., hand moves item into clothing/bag).	The concealment action ends (not for merely carrying a concealed item).	Sources and modifications			
Item	in_hand	The item is in direct hand contact with the shoplifter.	The item is put down or no longer in hand.	Source (modified)	What we selected	Count / format (as provided)	How we used it
Item	concealed	The item becomes hidden from view (placed inside clothing/bag).	Remains ON until the clip ends or the item becomes visible again.	UCF-Crime (subset)	Folders: Normal_Videos_for_Event_Recognition and Shoplifting	100 videos total (~50 normal + 50 shoplifting), MP4 320×240 @30 fps	Extracted clips manually person/item in used for both positive normal material.
Item	outside_property	The item is completely hidden and treated as removed from the store.	Not applicable within the same clip (terminal state).				

Table A.1.2: Source datasets and how we used them

- Boxes remain axis-aligned even if people/items rotate.
- If the camera crop hides part of an object/person, treat that as occlusion (not “missing”).
- Transparent packaging/glass: if the item is clearly visible, treat as visible, not occluded.

A.1.4 Edge-case guidance

- Heavy crowding: if multiple bodies overlap, prefer recall, keep a single tight box per individual when >50% is visible.
- Partial re-entry (only a hand/foot visible): do not re-activate the person track until >50% is visible.
- Reflections/monitors: ignore reflections unless the reflected item/person is physically present.
- Tiny/blurred items: if interaction is clear but the contour is uncertain, annotate with a conservative box around the visible region; mark concealed once it disappears into clothing/bag.

A. 1.5 Dataset & provenance

We built our training set shoplifting-surveillance-yolo-3GB (and the clip bundle surveillance-cvat-clips) from two public

Converted YOLO dataset (this run)

Table A.1.3: Training images by split

Split	Images	Background-only images	Notes
train	30,600	1,151	Cached from /labels/train; deterministic=True
val	9,836	785	Used for all metrics/curves reported
test	(held-out clips)	NA	Used only for final end-to-end decision metrics

Classes.nc: 2, names: ['person', 'item']
data.yaml. Points to images/train, images/val, images/test within the dataset root.

Training configuration

YOLOv10n was trained with Ultralytics 8.3.180 using the code below:

```
from ultralytics import YOLO

model = YOLO("yolov10n.pt")

results = model.train(

    data=yaml_path,

    epochs=50, imgsz=640, batch=16,

    workers=2, device=0, amp=True,

    cache=True,

    project="runs", name="y10n_shoplift",

    exist_ok=True

)

best_weights = "runs/detect/y10n_shoplift/weights/best.pt"
```

CLI equivalent

```
yolo detect train model=yolov10n.pt
data=$yaml_path imgsz=640 epochs=50 batch=16
\
workers=2 device=0 amp=True cache=True
project=runs name=y10n_shoplift
```

We constructed a frame-level YOLO dataset (shoplifting-surveillance-yolo-3GB) by sub-selecting videos from UCF-Crime (normal + shoplifting) and Pre-Crime (normal only), both in 320×240@30 fps MP4, then annotating person and item boxes in CVAT under a written occlusion policy (Appendix A.1). Splits were done by video/clip to prevent leakage. The final set contains 30,600 train and 9,836 validation images (plus background-only frames); classes are person and item. We trained YOLOv10n (Ultralytics 8.3.180) for 50 epochs at 640² with batch 16 on an A100, saving the best weights at runs/detect/y10n_shoplift/weights/best.pt. Source videos are 320×240 @ 30 fps; a subset was upsampled to 640-pixel width (4:3 → 640×480) using bicubic resampling, with frame rate and aspect ratio preserved. All frames are then letterboxed by Ultralytics to 640×640 at train/val time.

```
ffmpeg -i in.mp4 -vf "scale=640:-
2:flags=bicubic,fps=30" -c:v libx264 -crf 18
-preset veryfast -c:a copy out_640w.mp4
```